

IMPACT OF STRATEGIC LEADERSHIP ON ADMINISTRATIVE INNOVATION IN YEMENI INSURANCE COMPANIES IN SANA'A

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Abstract

The summary of the study: aimed to determine the impact of strategic leadership on administrative creativity in Yemeni insurance companies in the capital Sana'a. The researchers used a descriptive-analytical method and a questionnaire as a study tool. The study population included all employees in various job titles in the insurance companies in the study area. The researchers used a comprehensive census method for all study variables, which included 276 individuals in the specified job levels. The study hypotheses were tested using various statistical methods, and the study found several results, including: The level of strategic leadership practice in Yemeni insurance companies was high in all dimensions, with strategic determination being the most practiced dimension, and organizational culture enhancement being the least practiced. The level of administrative creativity was low in all dimensions (originality, fluency, flexibility, risk-taking, and sensitivity to problems). The study showed a statistically significant effect of strategic leadership dimensions (strategic determination, human capital development, balanced regulatory control implementation, ethical practices enhancement, and essential capabilities utilization) on administrative creativity in Yemeni insurance companies. However, there was no statistically significant effect of ethical practices enhancement on administrative creativity in Yemeni insurance companies. The study recommended creating a suitable work environment and climate for implementing company plans and programs and spreading leadership concepts and culture of creativity and innovation among employees and adopting cultures and employee participation in decision-making.

Keywords: Strategic Leadership, Administration Creativity.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Contemporary organizations operate in a complex and rapidly changing environment that imposes numerous and significant challenges on them. The world today witnesses many economic, political, social, and technological changes and transformations, and the business environment has become more challenging and complex. These continuous changes deeply affect the economic performance of countries in general and business organizations in particular. Improving performance and enhancing efficiency have become one of the most significant challenges facing business organizations to achieve their strategic objectives, acquire a high market share, and gain flexibility and sustainability (Al-Muaqabi, 2020). These changing and complex conditions affect organizational performance and have significant importance in managing organizations. Therefore, organizational performance has received

considerable attention from management thinkers and researchers since the industrial revolution to the present day. Organizations now look to individuals as one of the fundamental pillars, and they harness all their energies to change these individuals for the better and improve organizational performance in various ways, making them leaders in their respective fields (Fara, 2018).

Administrative creativity is one of the most important essentials in managing organizations and businesses. Successful organizations strive for excellence in ideas, performance, and objectives, and administrative creativity and innovation should be the distinctive feature of their services and performance. Administrative creativity plays an important role in the development and survival of the organization, as it helps it to face all contemporary problems and future challenges (Hatem, 2019).

Administrative creativity and innovation are the essence of any organization, and management scientists and practitioners agree that contemporary organizations live in a changing and complex environment, which makes them in urgent need of creativity to improve the capabilities of workers in generating ideas, keeping up with modern technological developments, solving problems, and participating in making appropriate decisions at the right time (Al-Sudai, 2021) Based on this, the researchers chose the topic of this study, which revolves around understanding the impact of strategic leadership on administrative creativity in Yemeni insurance companies in Sana'a.

2.0 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Yemeni insurance companies, in light of a series of economic transformations, suffer from weak leadership in improving organizational performance and have become unable to compete with foreign insurance companies even at the local level. This has led to the need to review the policies and marketing strategies of Yemeni insurance companies in order to be able to correct their marketing and competitive situation and raise their performance level. According to the indicators and annual reports issued by the Yemeni Insurance Federation for the years (2015-2022), Yemeni insurance companies suffer from weakness in administrative creativity.

Since the success of private organizations depends on the shoulders of strategic or administrative leadership and their ability to draw plans, visions, and policies based on deepening the culture of strategic planning in their institutions, as the top management alone can start the administrative creativity process, which enables the organization, including management and employees, to move towards work that leads to achieving strategic leadership. Due to the importance of the topic of administrative creativity. Through reviewing many reports and conference results on the activity of insurance companies in Yemen, which suffer from weak strategic leadership, it has led to a weakness in the administrative creativity of those researched companies. Due to the events that the country has been going through since 2011, which had a negative impact on the activity of insurance companies operating in Yemen, leading to a decline in the growth rates of premiums subscribed according to the 32nd General Conference of the Arab Insurance Federation held in Hammamet, Tunisia, from June 24-27, 2018., and according to what was mentioned in the financial annual reports of the Yemeni

insurance market for the years (2018-2022). Based on the previous studies above, a scientific gap was observed in the absence of a previous study that studies the variables of the current study. Therefore, the problem of this study lies in attempting to fill this research gap by studying the impact of strategic leadership on administrative creativity by applying it to Yemeni insurance companies - Sana'a. Therefore, the problem of the study can be identified and formulated in the following main question:

What is the Impact of Strategic Leadership on Administrative Creativity in Yemeni Insurance Companies - Sana'a?

This main question leads to a number of sub-questions, which are as follows:

- 1- What is the level of practicing strategic leadership in its dimensions in Yemeni insurance companies - Sana'a?
- 2- What is the level of administrative creativity in its dimensions in Yemeni insurance companies - Sana'a?
- 3- What is the level of practicing strategic leadership in administrative creativity attributed to demographic variables (gender, age, educational qualification, job title, years of service) in Yemeni insurance companies - Sana'a?

3.0 THE IMPORTANCE OF THIS STUDY

Lies in the importance of the study population, which is represented by Yemeni insurance companies in the capital Sana'a and their effective contributions to comprehensive and sustainable development. These companies have a significant impact on administrative creativity and its development in light of the rapid developments and technological advancements in information technology, data exchange, and the requirements of investors and customers in Yemeni insurance companies. Additionally, the importance of this study also lies in the scarcity of research and studies that have addressed the impact of strategic leadership on administrative creativity in Yemeni organizations in general and Yemeni insurance companies in particular. Therefore, the importance of this study can be summarized as follows:

3.1 Scientific Importance

The scientific importance of the study lies in the following:

- 1- The theoretical framework of the study can be a real addition to libraries and researchers in the field of general management and business administration by presenting a general framework for strategic leadership and administrative creativity, with its various fundamental dimensions.
- 2- The importance of this study lies in the importance of its variables (strategic leadership and administrative creativity), which are modern concepts in management literature that require further research, study, and analysis by future researchers to improve organizational performance.

3.2 Practical Importance

The practical importance of the study lies in the following:

- 1- The results of this study contribute to highlighting the necessary skills to promote and develop administrative creativity in Yemeni insurance companies in the capital Sana'a.
- 2- It is expected that this study will provide decision-makers in Yemeni insurance companies in the capital Sana'a with a real picture of the reality of strategic leadership practices and their continuous development and addressing any shortcomings if found.
- 3- The study will be conducted in profitable commercial organizations, which are Yemeni insurance companies that are important profitable organizations that suffer from administrative problems like any other commercial organization.

4.0 THE STUDY OBJECTIVES

To determine the impact of strategic leadership on administrative creativity in Yemeni insurance companies in the capital Sana'a, and this main objective will be achieved through the following sub-objectives:

- 1- Identifying the level of strategic leadership practice in Yemeni insurance companies in the capital Sana'a.
- 2- Identifying the level of administrative creativity achievement in Yemeni insurance companies in the capital Sana'a.
- 3- Knowing the level of statistically significant differences in the study sample's responses that relate to demographic variables (gender, age, educational qualification, job title, years of service) in Yemeni insurance companies in the capital Sana'a.

5.0 THE COGNITIVE MODEL OF THE STUDY

The model consists of two main variables:

- 1- **The independent variable:** strategic leadership represented by its dimensions (strategic determination, human capital development, organizational culture support and enhancement, balanced regulatory control implementation, ethical practices enhancement, essential capabilities utilization), which were selected based on reviewing many studies that addressed strategic leadership.
- 2- **The dependent variable:** administrative creativity represented by its dimensions (originality, fluency, flexibility, risk-taking, and sensitivity to problems), which were adopted based on previous studies that addressed administrative creativity.

The cognitive model of the study was prepared based on previous studies, including the Moroccan study (2023), the Hamdan study (2022), the Sada'i study (2021), the Rashid and Hamid study (2019), the Hooriya and Yousuf study (2019), the Al-Azani study (2018), the Al-Haza'a study (2018), the Ilyas, Munir, & Sobarsyah study (2017), the Lamiaa and Saham study

(2017), the Abu Hamour study (2017), the Hafez study (2017), the Moroccan study (2015), and the Juma and Nouri study (2011), as shown in Figure (1).

Figure 1: The Cognitive Model for the Study

6.0 STUDY HYPOTHESES

To answer the study's questions and objectives, the following hypotheses were formulated:

The Main Hypothesis

There is a statistically significant effect of strategic leadership on administrative creativity in

Yemeni insurance companies, and the following sub-hypotheses stem from this hypothesis:

- There is a statistically significant effect of determining strategic direction on administrative creativity in Yemeni insurance companies.
- There is a statistically significant effect of developing human capital on administrative creativity in Yemeni insurance companies.
- There is a statistically significant effect of supporting and enhancing organizational culture on administrative creativity in Yemeni insurance companies.
- There is a statistically significant effect of implementing balanced regulatory control on administrative creativity in Yemeni insurance companies..
- There is a statistically significant effect of promoting ethical practices on administrative creativity in Yemeni insurance companies.
- There is a statistically significant effect of utilizing core capabilities on administrative creativity in Yemeni insurance companies.

The Second Hypothesis: States that there are no significant differences between the sample's response averages towards the study's axes of strategic (leadership and administrative creativity) attributed to demographic variables such as (gender, age, educational qualification, job position, and years of service). This hypothesis branches into five sub-hypotheses, which are:

The First Sub-Hypothesis

There are no significant differences between the sample's response averages towards the study's axes of strategic leadership and administrative creativity attributed to gender.

The Second Sub-Hypothesis

There are no significant differences between the sample's response averages towards the study's axes of strategic leadership and administrative creativity attributed to educational qualification.

The Third Sub-Hypothesis

There are no significant differences between the sample's response averages towards the study's axes of strategic leadership and administrative creativity attributed to age.

The Fourth Sub-Hypothesis

There are no significant differences between the sample's response averages towards the study's axes of strategic leadership and administrative creativity attributed to years of service.

The Fifth Sub-Hypothesis

There are no significant differences between the sample's response averages towards the study's axes of strategic leadership and administrative creativity attributed to job position

7.0 DATA COLLECTION SOURCES

7.1 Primary Sources

The questionnaire method was used as the main tool for collecting data on the theoretical side of the study, including previous studies that will include a number of main and sub-axes related to strategic leadership in Yemeni insurance companies and its impact on the degree of organizational performance.

7.2 Secondary Sources

A number of secondary sources were used in this study, including scientific books that dealt with the theoretical aspects related to the subject of the study, namely strategic leadership and improving organizational performance, with their basic frameworks and dimensions, previous studies directly and indirectly related to the subject of the study, electronic websites, as well as relying on a number of reports, journals, and statistical bulletins related to the activity of Yemeni insurance companies, in addition to some references, literature, documents of Yemeni insurance companies, and some regulatory laws and regulations.

8.0 PREVIOUS STUDIES

A number of previous studies both direct and indirect, related to the topic of the study were reviewed, as follows:

Direct and indirect studies that addressed strategic leadership and organizational performance are:

- Moroccan study (2023): The study aimed to investigate the relationship between transformational leadership of leaders at the General Directorate of Education in Mecca and administrative creativity among administrators at the General Directorate of Education in Mecca. To achieve the objectives of the study, the descriptive analytical approach was used. The study population included a comprehensive survey sample, and the tools were applied to (56) administrators from the administrators at the General Directorate of Education in Mecca. The study concluded that the practice of transformational leadership and the level of administrative creativity of the administrators at the General Directorate of Education in Mecca were very high.
- Hamdan study (2022): The study aimed to identify the impact of strategic leadership in activating administrative creativity for employees at Avamia Pharmaceutical Industries Company. To achieve the objectives of the study, the descriptive analytical approach was used. The study population included employees working at Avamia, and the study sample consisted of (50) individuals from department managers and their deputies. The study concluded that there is a positive relationship between strategic leadership in its dimensions and administrative creativity for employees at Avamia Pharmaceutical Industries Company.

- Al-Saadi study (2021): The study aimed to identify the impact of strategic flexibility in achieving organizational performance through creativity in community colleges operating in the Republic of Yemen, in addition to identifying the extent of differences in the level of organizational performance, practicing strategic leadership, and identifying its impact on organizational performance in insurance companies in the capital Sana'a. To achieve the objectives of the study, the descriptive analytical approach was used. The study sample included employees and academics working in civil community colleges, with a total of (3,125) individuals, and the study sample consisted of (489) individuals. The study concluded that there is a positive impact of strategic flexibility in achieving organizational performance in community colleges in the Republic of Yemen.
- Rashid and Hamid study (2019): The study aimed to reveal the level of creative performance, in addition to trying to explore the extent to which the colleges in the study sample possess strategic flexibility that enables them to deal with changes in the external environment in a proactive or responsive manner. To achieve the objectives of the study, the descriptive analytical approach was used. The study sample consisted of private colleges from six Iraqi governorates, with a total of (38) colleges, and the study sample included (269) individuals. The study concluded that there is a relationship between strategic flexibility and creative performance.
- Study of Houria and Youssef (2019): The study aimed to reveal the role of transformational leadership in achieving administrative creativity through a field study on a sample of workers in one of the industrial institutions, Al-Lak Plus Company. To achieve the objectives of the study, the descriptive analytical approach was used. The study sample included a stratified random sample of Al-Lak Plus Company employees, and the study sample consisted of (63) individuals. The study concluded that the inspirational motivation of the transformational leader plays a role in achieving the strategic thinking of employees.
- Study of Al-Azzani (2018): The study aimed to identify the role of transformational leadership in its dimensions represented in (ideal influence, mental stimulation, empowerment of employees, inspirational motivation, and individual consideration) in developing administrative creativity represented in (accepting risk, authenticity, the ability to analyze and connect, mental flexibility, fluency, problem sensitivity) at Yemen Mobile, and to achieve the objectives of the study, the descriptive analytical approach was used. The study population included the stratified random sample of Yemen Mobile employees, where the study sample consisted of (137) individuals from the study population. The study concluded that the dimensions of transformational leadership are available to the leadership of Yemen Mobile Company with a high degree and the degree of elements of administrative creativity is available to employees at Yemen Mobile Company with a high degree.

- Study of Al-Hazh (2018): The study aimed to know the impact of leadership growth in determining the level of administrative creativity through the organizational culture in private universities. To achieve the objectives of the study, the descriptive analytical approach was used. The study sample included Yemeni private universities that have been established for more than ten years, and the study sample consisted of (320) individuals. The study concluded that there is an impact of leadership growth on the level of administrative creativity of individuals.
- Study of Ilyas, Munir, & Sobarsyah, (2017): The study aimed to know the relationship between strategic leadership, entrepreneurial orientation, creativity, and its impact on the performance of small businesses in south-Sulawesi. The study dimensions included strategic leadership, entrepreneurial orientation, creativity (independent), and institutional performance (dependent). To achieve the objectives of the study, the descriptive analytical approach was used. The study sample included a random sample of 100 small businesses. The study concluded that there is a positive relationship between strategic leadership, entrepreneurial orientation, and creativity on the performance of small businesses.
- Study of Lamia and Saham (2017): The study aimed to identify the concept of administrative leadership and administrative creativity and explain the dimensions and characteristics of the two concepts, considering that administrative creativity is a modern concept that has not been sufficiently researched at the Arab level. To achieve the objectives of the study, the descriptive analytical approach was used. The study population included the test of the commercial agency for communications of Algeria in the municipality of Milia, including three branches, and the study sample consisted of (30) individuals. The study concluded that there is an impact of the leadership style on administrative creativity, and therefore it is essential for the leader to have distinctive leadership qualities and be somewhat flexible, which makes him adopt methods and ways that encourage workers to take the initiative and be creative in work.
- Study of Abu Hamour (2017): The study aimed to identify the degree of availability of leadership practices that support administrative creativity among university leaders, represented by clients, agents, department heads, or supervisors at Port Said University. To achieve the objectives of the study, the descriptive analytical approach was used. The study sample included all licensed private hospitals in Jordan by the Jordanian Ministry of Health, with a total of (60) hospitals distributed in the northern, middle, and southern regions, and the study sample consisted of (261) researchers from the upper and middle management, medical and administrative departments, department heads, and supervisors who work in private hospitals. The study concluded that strategic leadership practices push the hospital to focus on creativity and organizational excellence and achieve high levels of performance and good reputation.

- Study of Hafiz (2017): The study aimed to investigate the impact of the nature of work and job position on leadership style. To achieve the objectives of the study, the descriptive analytical approach was used. The study population included all employees of the Saudi Company for Hotels and Tourism at different administrative levels. The study concluded that the hypotheses used in the research were proven.
- Study of Moroccan (2015): The study aimed to identify the reality of strategic leadership practices and administrative creativity in Palestinian universities in the Gaza Strip (Al-Azhar University, Islamic University, Al-Aqsa University) from the perspective of the senior administrative leaders in these universities, and then choose the relationship between strategic leadership and administrative creativity. To achieve the objectives of the study, the descriptive analytical approach was used. The study sample included members of the Palestinian university councils, totaling (64) individuals, and the study sample consisted of (54) individuals. The study concluded that strategic leadership practices are available in the researched universities at a high level with an average of (4.08).
- Study of Juma and Nouri (2011): The study aimed to test the relationship of correlation and impact between the variable of administrative leadership and the variable of administrative creativity. To achieve the objectives of the study, the descriptive analytical approach was used. The study sample included a random sample of (44) from Diyala University. The study concluded that administrative leadership is the key to accessing administrative creativity in organizations, and administrative creativity in turn is the key to accessing competitive advantage and organizations that are creative and leading.

9.0 PROCEDURAL TERMINOLOGY AND DEFINITIONS

9.1 Strategic Leadership

Strategic leadership is defined as a person's ability to predict, envision, maintain flexibility, engage in strategic thinking, and work with others to initiate changes that create a viable future for the organization to achieve specific goals that represent shared objectives (Faisal, 2017, p. 261).

It is also defined as "the process of influencing a group of individuals or employees in a specific position, directing them with the intention of gaining their trust and acceptance to develop the organizational culture of the organization, collaborating with them, supporting them, and leading them in their assigned tasks to achieve the organization's goals and develop it to ensure its progress" (I'qaba, 2017, p. 14)

It is defined as "the manager's ability to express a strategic vision for the organization or part of it, and to motivate and persuade others to obtain that vision" (Al-Habsi, 2021, p. 6).

Based on the above, strategic leadership can be defined as "the ability of commercial insurance companies to clarify the strategic vision of competitive organizations and encourage others to work according to this vision.

9.2 Administrative Innovation

It is defined as "the process of taking new and effective ideas to satisfy customer needs, and it is a continuous renewal and updating process that includes the entire institution and is an important part of business strategy and daily practices" (Awad, 2018, p. 6).

It is also defined as "an integrated unit of self and objective factors that lead to the creation of new solutions and ideas" (Zaqdo, 2015, p. 16).

It is also defined as breaking away from traditional thinking and knowledge by using one's mental abilities and surroundings to produce new and beneficial products for oneself and the society in which one lives (Sanusi, 2015, p. 8).

For the purposes of this study, administrative creativity is defined as: the innovation of a new mechanism for working in insurance companies through the optimal use of available resources in order to achieve the goal at the lowest cost and in the fastest possible time.

Authenticity: is defined as "the individual's ability to give new and diverse responses" (Al-Khalid, 2013, 4). It is also defined as renewal or uniqueness of ideas. A creative person with original thinking is one who deviates from the common or ordinary, and does not repeat the ideas of others. The ideas produced by such a person are considered new in light of the ideas that emerge from others, and this is one of the most important factors that make up the ability to think innovatively (Awad, 2018, 7).

For the purposes of this study, Authenticity is defined procedurally as: a creative person with original thinking who does not repeat the ideas of those around them.

Fluency: is "the ability to produce a larger number of synonyms, ideas, or uses when responding to a specific stimulus, and the speed in generating the ability to call up the largest possible number of ideas for a specific situation in a short and relative time" (Al-Ajla, 2009, 28).

It is also defined as the ability to produce large numbers of values and ideas within a certain period of time (Qaramash, 2014, 14).

For the purposes of this study, fluency is defined as the ability to create new ideas or alternatives quickly, including verbal and intellectual fluency.

Flexibility: It is defined as "the ability of an individual to think in more than one direction (Alkhaled2013, 4).

It is also defined as "looking at problems from multiple angles and gathering scattered ideas to come up with a new solution (Halawani, 1990, 63)."

For the purposes of this study, flexibility is defined as "the ability of an individual to easily change from one position to another.

Risk-taking: It is defined as "the courage of a person to expose them Selves to criticism or failure and defend their own ideas or work in a vague way (Alsafi 1997, 114)"

For the purposes of this study, risk-taking is defined as "the willingness to take risks resulting from the actions that the individual takes when adopting new ideas and methods and assuming responsibility for their consequences.

Problem sensitivity: The term "problem" refers to the ability to sense problems, understand their nature, and identify them (Khairallah 2009).

For the purposes of this study, problem sensitivity is defined as "the ability to sense problems, understand their nature, and identify them.

10. METHOD AND PROCEDURES OF THE STUDY

10.1 Study Method: The descriptive analytical method was used as one of the most commonly used methods in the study of social and human phenomena, which is consistent with the subject of the study. A questionnaire was also used to collect data from the study sample.

10.2 Study Population and Sample

A-Study population: The study population consists of leaders at all levels of Yemeni insurance companies in Sana'a, which number 18 companies according to reports from the Yemeni Insurance Federation and reports from the Ministry of Industry and Trade for the year 2020. **Study sample:** The study sample consists of leaders at all levels of Yemeni insurance companies in Sana'a.

Table 1: Yemeni Insurance Companies

#	Company Name	Year of Establishment	#	Company Name	Year of Establishment
1	Yemeni Insurance and Reinsurance Company	1969	10	Trust Yemen Insurance	1995
2	Marib Insurance	1974	11	Arab Insurance Company	1997
3	Yemen General Insurance Company	1977	12	Yemen Islamic Insurance Company	2001
4	United Insurance	1981	13	Al-Jazeera Insurance Company	2004
5	Yemen Insurance Company	1989	14	Specialized Health Insurance	2005
6	Four Health Insurance	1989	15	Yemen Qatar Insurance	2009
7	Saba Yemeni Insurance Company	1990	16	KAC Bank	2010
8	National Insurance Company	1993	17	Global Health Insurance Company	2019
9	AMAN Insurance	1993	18	Global Insurance Company	2021

B-Study Sample

This study focused on the leadership of Yemeni insurance companies in Sana'a, the capital city. The following companies were excluded from the study: International Insurance Company, Arab Insurance Company, and Four Health Insurance Company due to ownership differences, partnership dissolution, company fragmentation, or bankruptcy declaration. The study included

a total of 15 insurance companies. The comprehensive sampling method was used to represent the study population objectively, including all job titles (Chairman of the Board, General Manager, Deputy General Manager, Department Manager, Deputy Department Manager, and Department Head). This approach aimed to increase the statistical efficiency of the study and obtain accurate and generalizable results. The study sample consisted of 276 individuals, of which 216 responses were collected, as follows:

Table 2 illustrates the Yemeni insurance companies included in the study sample. It presents the names of these companies along with the hierarchical positions of their top leaders, ranging from Department Heads to Chairmen of the Board.

Table 2: Human Resources Department of Insurance Companies

5	Insurance Company Name	Year of Establishment	Chairman of the Board	Deputy Chairman of the Board	General Manager	Deputy General Manager	Deputy Director of Administration	Department Head	Total
1	Marib Insurance	1974	1	1	1	-	5	10	5
2	Yemen General Insurance	1977	1	1	1	1	2	7	2
3	United Insurance	1981	1	-	1	2	2	5	2
4	Yemen Insurance Company	1989	1	-	1	1	-	6	-
5	Saba Yemen Insurance	1990	1	-	1	1	-	8	-
6	National Insurance Company	1993	1	-	1	1	-	7	-
7	AMAN Insurance	1993	1	1	1	-	4	6	4
8	Trust Yemen Insurance	1995	1	-	1	1	4	4	4
9	Yemen Islamic Insurance	2001	1	1	1	1	1	9	1
10	Al-Jazeera Insurance	2004	1	-	1	1	-	6	-
11	Specialized Health Insurance	2005	1	-	1	1	3	3	3
12	Yemen Qatar Insurance	2009	1	-	1	1	1	6	1

13	KAC Bank	2010	1	1	1	-	-	10	-
14	Global Health Insurance	2019	1	-	1	1	-	6	-
15	Global Insurance Company	2021	-	1	1	1	-	5	-
Total	-	-	15	6	15	13	22	98	22

10.3 Study Tool

A questionnaire was used as the main tool for collecting data from the study sample. It included a number of paragraphs that covered 32 paragraphs in strategic leadership and 18 paragraphs in organizational performance. The questionnaire was validated by a number of faculty members at Yemeni universities. The reliability and stability were chosen using the Cronbach's alpha coefficient and the homogeneity coefficient for the variable, which showed the validity and stability of the study as follows:

10.4. The Reliability and Stability

I. Dimensions of Strategic Leadership-

A. The dimension of determining the strategic direction

The researcher calculated the discriminant validity measures of the scale, represented by the homogeneity coefficient of the latent variable Rho-A- the average of the explained variance AVE, and the results were as follows:

Figure 2: Paragraph Saturation with the Dimension of Strategic Orientation Defined

Table 3: Discriminant Validity Measures for the Dimension of Strategic Orientation

AVE	Rho-A	Scal Value
0.68	0.93	

It is evident from Figure (2) and Table (3) that the saturation of items in the dimension of strategic orientation was high, exceeding the minimum saturation threshold (0.30). The values of the discriminant validity measures, represented by the homogeneity coefficient for the latent variable Rho-A and the average explained variance (AVE), were (0.93, 0.68), surpassing the minimum threshold for discriminant validity, which is 0.5 for the AVE and the minimum threshold for scale homogeneity, which is 0.7. This indicates that the items in the dimension of strategic orientation are characterized by high validity and homogeneity, representing the dimension.

B. Dimension of Human Capital Development

The researcher calculated the discriminant validity measures for the scale, represented by the homogeneity coefficient for the latent variable Rho-A and the average explained variance (AVE), and the results were as follows:

Figure 3: Saturation of Paragraphs in the Dimension of Developing Human Capital

Table 4: Discriminant Validity Measures for the Dimension of Developing Human Capital

AVE	Rho-A	Scale
0.57	0.78	Value

It is evident from Figure (3) and Table (4) that the saturation of paragraphs in the dimension of developing human capital was high, exceeding the minimum saturation threshold (0.30). Additionally, the discriminant validity measures, represented by the (Rho-A latent variable homogeneity coefficient and the average variance extracted (AVE)), were (0.78, 0.57), exceeding the minimum threshold for discriminant validity, which is set at 0.5 for AVE and 0.7 for the homogeneity coefficient. This indicates that the paragraphs in the dimension of developing human capital are characterized by high validity and homogeneity and represent the dimension well.

C. Constructing the Organizational Culture Enhancement Dimension

The researcher calculated the discriminant validity measures of the construct, which included the Rho-A homogeneity coefficient for the latent variable and the average variance extracted (AVE). The results were as follows:

Figure 4: Paragraphs Saturation of the Dimension of Enhancing Organizational Culture

Table 5: Discriminatory Reliability Measures for the Dimension of Enhancing Organizational Culture

AVE	Rho-A	Scale Value
0.70	0.92	

It is evident from Figure (4) and Table (5) that the paragraphs saturation of the dimension of enhancing organizational culture was high, exceeding the minimum saturation threshold (0.30). Also, the values of the discriminatory reliability measures represented by (the homogeneity coefficient of the latent variable Rho-A - the average variance extracted AVE) were (0.92, 0.70), exceeding the minimum threshold for discriminatory reliability, which is set at 0.5 for the average variance extracted AVE and 0.7 for the homogeneity of the scale. This indicates that the paragraphs of the dimension of enhancing organizational culture are characterized by high reliability and homogeneity and represent the dimension.

D. After Implementing Balanced Regulatory Control

The researcher calculated the discriminant validity measures of the scale, represented by the homogeneity coefficient of the latent variable Rho-A, the explained variance average (AVE), and the results were as follows:

Figure 5: Shows the Factor Loadings after Implementing Balanced Regulatory Control

Table 6: Shows the Discriminant Validity Measures after Implementing Balanced Regulatory Control

AVE	Rho-A	Scale Value
0.62	0.89	

As shown in Figure (5) and Table (6), the factor loadings after implementing balanced regulatory control were high and exceeded the minimum saturation threshold (0.30). The discriminant validity measures, represented by the homogeneity coefficient of the latent variable Rho-A and the explained variance average (AVE), were (0.89, 0.62), exceeding the minimum discriminant validity threshold of 0.5 for AVE and the minimum homogeneity threshold of 0.7 for the scale, indicating that the factor after implementing balanced regulatory control is characterized by high validity and homogeneity and represents the dimension

E. After Implementing Ethical Practices

The researcher calculated the homogeneity coefficient of the latent variable Rho-A and the explained variance average (AVE), and the results were as follows:

Figure 6: Shows the Factor Loadings after Implementing Ethical Practices

Table 7: Shows the Discriminant Validity Measures after Implementing Ethical Practices

AVE	Rho-A	Scale
0.57	0.85	Value

According to figure 6 and table 7, it is evident that the saturation of paragraphs with the dimension of ethical practices enhancement was high and exceeded the minimum saturation threshold of (0.30). Additionally, the values of the discriminant validity measures represented by the homogeneity coefficient of the latent variable Rho-A and the explained variance average (AVE) reached(0.85. 0.57) respectively, exceeding the minimum threshold of discriminant validity set at 0.5 for the AVE measure and the minimum homogeneity of the scale and the determinant are 0.7, indicating that the paragraphs of the ethical practices enhancement dimension are characterized by high sincerity and homogeneity and represent the dimension.

F. Essential Estimates Dimension

The researcher calculated the discriminant validity measures of the scale, represented by the homogeneity coefficient of the latent variable Rho-A, the explained variance average (AVE), and the results were as follows:

Figure 7: Saturation of the Paragraphs of the Essential Estimates Dimension

Table 8: Discriminant Validity Measures for the Essential Estimates Dimension

AVE	Rho-A	Scale
0.59	0.88	Value

It is evident from Figure (7) and Table (8) that the saturation of the paragraphs of the essential estimates dimension was high, exceeding the minimum saturation threshold (0.30). The discriminant validity measures, represented by the homogeneity coefficient of the latent variable Rho-A and the explained variance average (AVE), were (0.59, 0.88), exceeding the minimum discriminant validity threshold of 0.5 for the AVE and the minimum homogeneity of the scale and the determinant of 0.7, indicating that the paragraphs of the essential estimates dimension are characterized by high sincerity and homogeneity and represent the dimension.

II. Administrative Creativity

A. Authenticity Dimension

The researcher calculated the discriminant validity measures of the scale, represented by the homogeneity coefficient of the latent variable Rho-A, the explained variance average (AVE), and the results were as follows:

Figure 8: Saturation of the Paragraphs of the Authenticity Dimension

Table 9: Discriminant Validity Measures for the Authenticity Dimension

AVE	Rho-A	Scale Value
0.50	0.82	

It is evident from Figure (8) and Table (27) that the saturation of the paragraphs of the authenticity dimension was high, exceeding the minimum saturation threshold (0.30). The discriminant validity measures, represented by the homogeneity coefficient of the latent variable Rho-A and the explained variance average (AVE), were (0.50, 0.82), exceeding the minimum discriminant validity threshold of 0.5 for the AVE and the minimum homogeneity of the scale and the determinant of 0.7, indicating that the paragraphs of the authenticity dimension are characterized by high sincerity and homogeneity and represent the dimension

B. Flexibility Dimension

The researchers calculated the discriminant validity measures of the scale, represented by the homogeneity coefficient of the latent variable Rho-A, the explained variance average (AVE), and the results were as follows:

Figure 9: Saturation of the Paragraphs of the Flexibility Dimension

Table 10: Discriminant Validity Measures for the Flexibility Dimension

AVE	Rho-A	Scale
0.68	0.91	Value

It is evident from Figure (9) and Table (10) that the saturation of the paragraphs of the flexibility dimension was high, exceeding the minimum saturation threshold (0.30). The discriminant validity measures, represented by the homogeneity coefficient of the latent variable Rho-A and the explained variance average (AVE), were (0.86, 0.91), exceeding the minimum discriminant validity threshold of 0.5 for the AVE and the minimum homogeneity of the scale and the determinant of 0.7, indicating that the paragraphs of the flexibility dimension are characterized by high sincerity and homogeneity and represent the dimension.

C. Fluency Dimension

The researchers calculated the discriminant validity measures of the scale, represented by the homogeneity coefficient of the latent variable Rho-A, the explained variance average (AVE), and the results were as follows:

Figure 10: Saturation of the Paragraphs of the Fluency Dimension

Table 11: Discriminant Validity Measures for the Fluency Dimension

AVE	Rho-A	Scale
0.70	0.90	Value

It is evident from Figure (10) and Table (11) that the saturation of the paragraphs of the fluency dimension was high, exceeding the minimum saturation threshold (0.30). The discriminant validity measures, represented by the homogeneity coefficient of the latent variable Rho-A and the explained variance average (AVE), were (0.70, 0.90), exceeding the minimum discriminant validity threshold of 0.5 for the AVE and the minimum homogeneity of the scale and the determinant of 0.7, indicating that the paragraphs of the fluency dimension are characterized by high sincerity and homogeneity and represent the dimension.

E- Risk Dimension

The researchers calculated the discriminant validity measures of the scale, represented by the homogeneity coefficient of the latent variable Rho-A, the explained variance average (AVE), and the results were as follows:

Figure 11: Saturation of the Paragraphs of the Risk Dimension

Table 12: Discriminant Validity Measures for the Risk Dimension

AVE	Rho-A	Scale
0.74	0.94	Value

It is evident from Figure (11) and Table (12) that the saturation of the paragraphs of the risk dimension was high, exceeding the minimum saturation threshold (0.30). The discriminant validity measures, represented by the homogeneity coefficient of the latent variable Rho-A and the explained variance average (AVE), were (0.74, 0.94), exceeding the minimum discriminant validity threshold of 0.5 for the AVE and the minimum homogeneity of the scale and the determinant of 0.7, indicating that the paragraphs of the risk dimension are characterized by high sincerity and homogeneity and represent the dimension.

F. Problem Sensitivity Dimension

The researchers calculated the discriminant validity measures of the scale, represented by the homogeneity coefficient of the latent variable Rho-A, the explained variance average (AVE), and the results were as follows:

Figure 12: Saturation of the Paragraphs of the Problem Sensitivity Dimension

Table 13: Discriminant Validity Measures for the Problem Sensitivity Dimension

AVE	Rho-A	Scale Value
0.66	0.91	

It is evident from Figure (12) and Table (13) that the saturation of the paragraphs of the problem sensitivity dimension was high, exceeding the minimum saturation threshold (0.30). The discriminant validity measures, represented by the homogeneity coefficient of the latent variable Rho-A and the explained variance average (AVE), were (0.66, 0.91), exceeding the minimum discriminant validity threshold of 0.5 for the AVE and the minimum homogeneity of the scale and the determinant of 0.7, indicating that the paragraphs of the problem sensitivity dimension are characterized by high sincerity and homogeneity and represent the dimension.

11. DISTRIBUTING A SAMPLE FOR STUDY ACCORDING TO THE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SAMPLE INDIVIDUALS

The researcher in this section divides the study sample according to personal and functional variables, where the research sample was distributed as follows:

1- Distribution of the research sample gender

Table 14: Shows the Distribution of the Research Simple by Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage%
Male	148	68.5
Female	68	31.5
Total	216	100.0

Table (14) shows that the percentage of males is higher than females, where the percentage of females (31.5%) compared to the percentage of males (68.5%). The researcher attributes this to the employment opportunities provided to males more than females, which is consistent with the prevailing environment in Yemen, where the male workforce dominates the work environment.

2- Distribution of the Research Sample by Age

Table 15: Shows the Distribution of the Research Sample by Age

Age groups	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 25 Years	6	2.8
25.- less than 35 years	94	43.5
36 – less than 45 years	85	39.4
From 24 years and above	31	14
Total	216	100.0

The above table (15) indicates that the majority of employees in Yemeni insurance companies are concentrated in the age group of (25 - less than 35 years), representing a percentage of (43.5%) of the total. The number of employees in Yemeni insurance companies in the age group of (36 - less than 45 years) comes in second place with a percentage of (39.4%), while the number of employees in Yemeni insurance companies in the age group of (45 years and above) comes in third place, representing 14%. The age group of employees in Yemeni insurance companies who are less than 25 years old comes in fourth place with a low percentage of (2.8%)

3- Distribution of the Research Sample by Qualification

Table 16: Shows the Distribution of the Research Sample by Qualification

Qualification	Frequency	Percentage%
High school	7	3.2
Bachelor's degree	175	81
Higher diploma	19	8.8
Master's degree	13	6
Doctorate	2	0.9
Total	216	100.0

The above table (16) shows that employees in Yemeni insurance companies with a bachelor's degree ranked first with a percentage of (81%). Employees in Yemeni insurance companies with a higher diploma ranked second with a percentage of (8.8%), while employees in Yemeni insurance companies with a master's degree ranked third with a percentage of (6%). Employees in Yemeni insurance companies with a high school diploma and a doctorate degree ranked last with a percentage ranging from (0.9% - 3.2%). These indicators enhance the positivity and reliability of the results of this study due to the good scientific background of the sample.

4- Distribution of the Research Sample by Years of Experience

Table 17: Shows the Distribution of the Research Sample by Years of Experience

Years of experience	Frequency	Percentage%
Less than 5 years	44	20.4
5 – less than 10 years	54	25
10 - less than 15 years	49	22.7
From 15 years and above	69	32
Total	216	100

Above table (17) shows that the number of employees in Yemeni insurance companies who have (15 years and above) of experience ranked first with a percentage of (32%). Employees in Yemeni insurance companies who have (5 - less than 10 years) of experience ranked second with a percentage of (25%), while the number of employees in Yemeni insurance companies who have (10 - less than 15 years) of experience ranked third with a percentage of (22.7%). The number of employees in Yemeni insurance companies who have (less than 5 years) of experience ranked last with a percentage of (20.4%). This indicates the presence of accumulated experiences among the employees represented in the study sample. The more years of service and professional experience the employees have, the more capable they are of forming positive opinions about the subject of the study and its variables.

5- Distribution of the Research Sample by Job Title

Table 18: Shows the Distribution of the Research Sample by Job Title

Job Title	Frequency	Percentage%
Chairman of the Board	15	6.94
Deputy Chairman of the Board	6	2.78
General Manager	15	6.94
Deputy General Manager	13	6.02
Department Manager	98	45.37
Deputy Department Manager	22	10.16
Section Head	107	49.45
Total	2016	100

The above table (18) shows that employees in the job title of (Section Head) ranked first with a percentage of (49.54%). Employees in the job title of (Department Manager) ranked second with a percentage of (45.37%). Employees in the job title of (Deputy Department Manager) ranked third with a percentage of (10.16%). Employees in the job titles of (Chairman of the Board - General Manager) ranked fourth with a percentage of (6.94%). Employees in the job title of (Deputy General Manager) ranked fifth with a percentage of (6.02%). Employees in the job title of (Vice Chairman of the Board) ranked last with a percentage of (2.78%).

12. DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF STUDY VARIABLES

In this section, the researchers used means, standard deviations, and relative importance to analyze the dimensions and phrases of the questionnaire related to strategic leadership and organizational performance.

The Descriptive Analysis of the Study Dimensions

Is shown in the following table number (19), which includes the overall mean, standard deviation, rank, and relative importance of the study dimensions

Table 19: Shows that the Employees' Responses to the Dimension

Table No	Dimensions	weighted average	standard deviation	Rank	Direction	Relative weight
strategic leadership						
1	Determine strategic direction	5.68	0.22	1	Agree	81.22
2	developing human capital"	5.38	0.31	5	Agree	76.93
3	Developing and improving organizational culture	5.22	0.09	6	Fairly agree	74.65
4	Implementing balanced regulatory control	5.63	0.05	2	Agree	80.51
5	Promoting ethical Practices	5.60	0.36	3	Agree	80.08
6	Essential estimates Dimension	5.53	0.26	4	Agree	79.08
	average General	5.507				
	standard deviation	0.175			Agree	
organizational performance						
1	Efficiency	5.59	0.016		Agree	79.94
2	Effectiveness	5.38	0.017		Agree	76.93
	General average	5.485			Agree	
	Standard deviation	0.148				

It is evident from Table 19 that

Strategic Leadership Variable

The average for the strategic leadership variable was (5.507) with a standard deviation of (0.175) and a favorable direction. Regarding the dimensions of this variable, it is noted that the "determination of strategic direction" dimension ranked first with an average of 5.68 a standard deviation of 0.22, and a favorable direction. Meanwhile, the "enhancement of organizational culture" dimension ranked last with an average of 5.22, a standard deviation of 0.09, and a somewhat favorable direction.

Organizational Performance Variable

The average for the organizational performance variable was (5.485) with a standard deviation of (0.148) and a favorable direction. Regarding the dimensions of this variable, it is noted that the "efficiency" dimension ranked first with an average of 5.59, a standard deviation of 0.16, and a favorable direction. Meanwhile, the "effectiveness" dimension ranked last with an average of 5.38, a standard deviation of 0.17, and a favorable direction.

13. THE STRUCTURAL MODEL AND TESTING THE STUDY HYPOTHESES

This section includes the structural model of the study and testing its hypotheses

The structural model of the study: shows the structural relationships of the study variables, which are the independent variable of strategic leadership and its dimensions (determination of strategic direction, development of human capital, enhancement of organizational culture, implementation of balanced regulatory control, and enhancement of ethical practices) and the dependent variable of organizational performance and its dimensions (efficiency and effectiveness).

Figure 13: Shows the Structural Model of the Study Variables

Testing the Hypotheses of the Study

The First Hypothesis

There is a statistically significant direct effect of strategic leadership (determining strategic direction, developing human capital, enhancing organizational culture, implementing balanced regulatory control, and promoting ethical practices) on administrative creativity in Yemeni insurance companies at a significance level of (0.05).

To test the hypothesis, the researcher used the structural regression analysis method, and the results were as follows:

Table 20: Results of the Structural Regression Model for Strategic Leadership and Administrative Creativity

Dependent Variable / Administrative Creativity										
Calculated, Significance Level,			Model Matching Indicators R ²	Correlation Coefficient R	Test T		Standard Error	Model Features Standardization		Independent Variables Strategic leadership
GOF	Effect Size Coefficient F	Q ₂			Significance Level	Calculated		B ₁	B ₂	
0.72	0.012	0.32	0.55	0.74	0.003	3.021	0.034	-0.102	B ₁	Determining strategic direction
	0.031				0.000	4.831	0.041	0.202	B ₂	Developing human capital
	0.012				0.000	4.446	0.042	0.188	B ₃	Enhancing organizational culture
	0.02				0.000	4.835	0.030	0.149	B ₄	Implementing balanced regulatory control
	0.001				0.283	1.074	0.033	0.034	B ₅	Promoting ethical practices
	0.082				0.000	8.713	0.042	0.360	B ₆	Essential estimates dimension

The table (20) shows a strong correlation between the independent variables of the dimensions of strategic leadership (determining strategic direction, developing human capital, enhancing organizational culture, implementing balanced regulatory control, and promoting ethical practices) and the dependent variable of administrative creativity. This is confirmed by the Pearson correlation coefficient, which was (0.74) and statistically significant at a level of significance of (0.05). The results of the structural analysis of the dimensions of strategic leadership, which include (determining strategic direction, developing human capital, enhancing organizational culture, implementing balanced regulatory control, promoting ethical practices, and core competencies), and administrative creativity were (-0.102, 0.202, 0.188, 0.149, 0.034, 0.360), respectively, all of which have a significant effect on administrative creativity,

Except for Promoting Ethical Practices: The direct impact of the independent variables on administrative creativity is ranked as follows: core competencies, developing human capital, enhancing organizational culture, implementing balanced regulatory control, determining strategic direction, It is statistically significant at a morale level of 0.05, except after the promotion of ethical practices, which was shown by the (T) test of the parameters of the model. The impact of the dimensions of strategic leadership, which include (determining strategic

direction, developing human capital, enhancing organizational culture, implementing balanced regulatory control, and promoting ethical practices), on administrative creativity is (0.56), in the presence of the dependent variable performance of the organizational the rate of (0.44) back to other factors not included in the model as seen from the table that the value of the most important indicators of the conformity of the proposed model to the data of the study of (explanatory power index of the structural model (Q²), reliability index of the structural model, GOF) amounted to (0.50 and 0.72) successively, which exceeded a minimum level of comparison (Q²>0, the GOF>0.1) effect coefficient of the independent variable dimensions comparison (F² (0.082, 0.001, 0.02, 0.012, 0.031, 0.012) successively, which exceeded a minimum level of comparison (F² ≥ 0.02) Therefore, the second main hypothesis is accepted, which states that there is a statistically significant direct effect of strategic leadership (determining strategic direction, developing human capital, enhancing organizational culture, implementing balanced regulatory control, promoting ethical practices, and core competencies) on administrative creativity in Yemeni insurance companies at a significance level of (0.05).

The Second Hypothesis states that there are no significant differences in the means of the sample individuals' responses towards the study axes represented in (strategic leadership - administrative creativity) attributed to personal and functional characteristics at a significance level of (0.05). And it branches into the following hypotheses:

The First Sub-Hypothesis: states that there are no significant differences in the means of the sample individuals' responses towards the study axes represented in (strategic leadership - administrative creativity) attributed to gender at a significance level of (0.05).

Table 21: Shows the Results of the T-test for Two Independent Samples for the Study Axes According to Gender

Axis	Gender	Mean	Mean Differences	T	Significance Level	Decision
Strategic Leadership	Male	5.502	0.03425	-0.248	0.804	No significant differences
Strategic Leadership	Female	5.5363				
Administrative Creativity	Male	5.3497	0.03262	-0.248	0.805	No significant differences
Administrative Creativity	Female	5.3824				

The table number (21) shows that there are no significant differences in the means of the sample's responses towards the study's axes, represented in (strategic leadership - administrative creativity), attributed to gender at a significance level of (0.05). This was confirmed by the T-test for a single sample, where the calculated value of (T) for the study's axes (-0.248, -0.248) respectively, was not statistically significant at a significance level of (0.05). Therefore, we accept the first sub-hypothesis, which states that there are no significant differences in the means of the sample's responses towards the study's axes, represented in (strategic leadership - administrative creativity), attributed to gender at a significance level of (0.05).

The Second Sub-Hypothesis: states that there are no significant differences in the means of the sample's responses towards the study's axes, represented in (strategic leadership - administrative creativity), attributed to qualification at a significance level of (0.05). To test this hypothesis, the researcher used one-way ANOVA.

Table 22: Shows the Results of the One-Way ANOVA Test for the Means of the Respondents' Responses to the Study Axes According to Qualification

Decision	Significance Level	F-value	Arithmetic by qualification	The Qualification	Axis	
No significant differences	.6900	.5630	5.7429	High school	Strategic Leadership	1
			5.4676	Bachelor's degree		
			5.6474	Higher diploma		
			5.7538	Master's degree		
			5.8167	Doctorate		
No significant differences	.6040	.6840	5.5657	High school	Administrative Creativity	2
			5.3113	Bachelor's degree		
			5.5832	Higher diploma		
			5.5631	Master's degree		
			5.4600	Doctorate		

From table number (22), it is clear that there are no significant differences between the means of the sample respondents' answers towards the study axes represented in (strategic leadership - administrative creativity - organizational performance) attributed to the qualification, and this is what was explained by the one-way ANOVA test, where the calculated value of (F) for the study axes (0.684, 0.563) successively, and they are not statistically significant at a significance level of (0.05). Therefore, we accept the second sub-hypothesis, which states that there are no significant differences between the means of the sample respondents' answers towards the study axes represented in (strategic leadership - administrative creativity) attributed to the qualification at a significance level of (0.05).

The Third Sub-Hypothesis

There are no significant differences between the means of the sample respondents' answers towards the study axes represented in (strategic leadership - administrative creativity) attributed to age at a significance level of (0.05).

To test the hypothesis, the researcher used one-way ANOVA, and the results were as follows:

Table 23: Result of One-Way ANOVA Test for the Means of Respondents' Answers to the Study Axes by Age

Axis	Age	Mean	F-value	Significance level	Decision
Strategic leadership	Less than (25) years	5.5556	0.979	0.404	No significant differences
	25 and less than 35 years	5.6149			
	36 and less than 45 years	5.3773			
	45 years and above	5.5578			
Administrative creativity	Less than (25) years	5.9933*	3.957	0.009	Significant differences
	25 and less than 35 years	5.5072			
	36 and less than 45 years	5.1261			
	45 years and above	5.4187			

*Significant differences according to LSD test

Table number (23) shows that there were no significant differences between the means of the sample respondents' answers towards the study axes represented in (strategic leadership - administrative creativity) attributed to age, as indicated by the one-way ANOVA test, where the calculated (F values) for the study axes were (3.957,0.979) successively, and they were not statistically significant at a significance level of (0.05). **Therefore**, we accept the third sub-hypothesis regarding strategic leadership and administrative creativity.

14. CONCLUSIONS

The Conclusions Related to the Study Variables are

- 1) Weak participation of relevant parties in developing the strategic vision and lack of clarity of insurance companies' goals by all employees.
- 2) Shortcomings in developing human capital in companies through weak incentives and rewards for outstanding employees, shortcomings in developing and training employees in companies, and not empowering employees and giving them sufficient authority.
- 3) Weakness or lack of interest of insurance companies in promoting organizational culture, which is manifested in not providing the appropriate environment for implementing the companies' plans and programs, not encouraging their leadership to adopt a culture of creativity and innovation and decision-making, and not giving great importance to promoting the culture for employees.
- 4) There are shortcomings in promoting ethical practices within companies through the lack of commitment of their leaders to the values of justice and equality in dealing with employees.
- 5) Weakness in the material and moral motivation policies for employees, and shortcomings in policies for selecting and appointing employees with outstanding abilities and skills in companies.

- 6) Yemeni insurance companies apply strategic leadership to a high degree and in all its dimensions, and the level of interest and practice in promoting organizational culture was less than the other dimensions.
- 7) Decreased job satisfaction of employees and weak incentives that lead to improving performance.
- 8) Weak coherence and cooperation among employees during work execution..
- 9) Shortcomings of employees in producing new ideas for work or presenting innovative solutions to problems and weak communication skills of employees.
- 10) Employees cling to traditional work methods and do not keep up with technological developments in the work environment.
- 11) Weakness and inability of employees to provide appropriate ideas or alternatives for situations they face at work.
- 12) Weak risk-taking among employees and inability to adopt new ideas and not taking responsibility for their work results.
- 13) Inability of employees to predict problems before they occur and weakness in discovering problems that others suffer from and not having plans to face those problems.

Recommendations: The

- 1) The need to involve all relevant parties in developing the vision and mission of insurance companies and clarifying their goals.
- 2) The need to focus on developing human capital through adopting policies of incentives and rewards for outstanding employees, implementing specialized and diverse training programs to develop employees in companies, and giving employees more empowerment to accomplish their tasks.
- 3) The need to create a suitable work environment and climate to implement the plans and programs of companies, and to spread the concepts and culture of creativity and innovation among employees, and to adopt cultures of sharing and involving employees in decision-making.
- 4) The need to promote ethical practices for companies, and to adopt justice and equality in dealing with all employees.
- 5) The need to develop programs for the system of material and moral incentives in companies that meet the needs of employees, and to adopt a clear policy in selecting and appointing employees with outstanding skills.
- 6) Working to achieve job satisfaction for employees and focusing on incentives that lead to improving their performance.

- 7) Working to create an environment and climate that strengthens or increases harmony and cooperation among employees, and providing modern technologies that help accomplish work in less time.
- 8) Encouraging and motivating employees to produce and present innovative ideas in the field of work, solving problems, and developing effective communication skills for employees.
- 9) Encouraging employees to adopt innovative work methods and developing and training employees to keep up with modern technology in the work environment.
- 10) Developing the capabilities of employees to produce ideas and alternatives to face different work problems.
- 11) Encouraging employees to adopt new ideas and take responsibility for the results, no matter what the risks are.
- 12) Developing the skills of employees in predicting, analyzing, and diagnosing problems before they occur, and training employees to plan to face problems and provide necessary alternatives.

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